

Organisational diagnosis and importance of Management information system

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ABSTRACT

This article discussing organisational diagnosis for effective functioning of organisation. Organisation is gist of our life and development. Donhem says that if our civilization falls down it will be failure of administration. To trace organisational diagnosis three things are required strength, weakness and potential. Information technology and information management is another important factor to revive and protect any organisation. Two aspects of organisations should be apparently explained. Structural aspects (subsystem and various components) and procedure/process. Communication is life line to connect each and every part of subsystem. So, discussing organisational diagnosis it's important to include continuation of information management system. Information system based on transaction, events and data. It uses set of procedure and technologies for better efficiency and results.

Key words: IMS, Diagnosis, Subsystem, Information Technology, Telecommunication, Work Force, Structural Aspect.

ORGANIZATION

Organisation is a group of people who work together to get a set goal. It is a gist of all management system which associates different components of work.

Fig-1

Organisation is a specific mechanism that enables different and various parts to go along with for a common goal. Thus we can say organisation is a process, framework of relationships and a group of persons, according to CHESTER BERNARD- Organisation is a system of co-operative activities of two or more persons." HANKEY

says that organisation is a harmonious adjustment of specialised parts for the accomplishment of some common purposes. Examples of organisations are- Governments, NGOs Armed forces etc.

As we know organisational structure (OS) is the systematic arrangement of Human resources. It outlines the role and responsibilities of personnel for smooth functioning of organisation.

Now we can say that organisation is a structure and functioning of Human System consisting different subsystems. Ecology of an organisation depends on various elements which are visible or invisible. When the human system in trouble it could be either any negativity in a part or problem in subpart. When are organisation derails in its functioning, there could be many reasons relating different levels of organisational set-up organisation has several levels and mindsets so the complexity or problems have multifaceted forms so, as just a doctor organisation and specialist effort to solve the problem. Here, organisational Diagnosis becomes important part of any organisation.

What is organisational diagnosis

(i) Organisational diagnosis is an exercise attempted to make an analysis the organisation, its structure, subsystems and process in order to identify strength and weakness of its components. (IGNOU, MGSE Block I, Unit – 4 page No. 2)

(ii) Organisational diagnosis is a process based upon behavioural science theory for publicly entering a human system collecting valid data about human experiences with that system, and feeding that information back to the system to promote increased understanding of the system by its members. (Alderfor 1981)

Purpose of organisational analysis organisational diagnosis important steps

- (i) Organisational subsystem – Every organisation can be conceived of various subsystems on parts. Effective functioning base is co-ordination and informed subsystem. As Behave has said that – development of a strategy for systematic improvement of an organisation demands an examination of present state things. So, we can point out that
- Various levels in organisation like Top management, middle management, grade I officer etc.
 - Geographical units, like regions wise, state wise.
 - functional based subsystems as engineering wing. Research wings. finance wing
 - Division based – as Production automation etc.

Organisational Process

There are several aspects of organisational process.

- Communication – we can listed communication openners, communication different ways (upworeds downward, sharing etc.)
- Goal setting – How are goals set, clarity of goals, process to achieve goals.
- Motivation – Motivation mechanism regularity, promotion, financeial benefit etc.
- Role clarity – Ambiquity of role flexibility in role playing, rigidity periodic dialogue.
- Culture – what are the norms and values in the organisation that are shared equally? Opening mutual thirst, collaborative attitude, risk taking mindset.

Besides this conflicts management teamwork, grivances redressal system, arrangement styles and organisational learning mechanism are another importatn factors to look up and down a organisation.

Organisational analysis has various aim and purposes these include –

- i. To promote and enhance general understanding of the functioning of an organisation.
- ii. Improving efficiency and competency
- iii. Problem solving management mechanism.
- iv. Planning for growth and diversification.
- v. Effective communication and information management system.

Organisational Analysis Perspective

For diagnosis of an organisation there could be used some perspective following the aim and targets of that organisation.

- i. Economic Perspective

- a. Use of money
- b. Allocation of material
- ii. (ii) Sociological
 - a. Individual behaviour
 - b. Social behaviour
- iii. Psychological
 - a. Attitude
 - b. Aptitude
 - c. Strike
 - d. Indiscipline
- iv. Political science
 - a. factics strategies
 - b. Quest for power, powered
- v. Management
- vi. Applied behavioural science perspective

Fig-2

INFORMATION, MANAGEMENT AND INFORMATION SYSTEM

Information Management and Information system is gist to make an organisation scientific. It is a business and process driven concept in which the focus a leveraging information for using it to take decision on the quality of such information that is provided and the integrity of the informatino. IGNOU (MGSE) Management Information System (MIS) facilitate transactions, events and data. It provided systematic process involving information, gathering, storing, processing, retrieving insuing repeatability of good quality information supply within organisation.

When we define Management information system it includes data processing and providing works which helps managers at all levels. They can use these data in making planning for decision making and in programme implementation. In this way management information system comprises of all contents that are useful in automobilisation of organisation.

Finally, according to Jerome – "Management information system is a system that aids management in making carrying out and controlling decisions.

Importance of Management Information system in diagnosis of organisation.

There are many reason which are increasing importance of Management Information System (MIS)

- i. Globalization and Liberalization
- ii. Enhancing Outsourcing tendency
- iii. Increasing importance of civil Society and media.
- iv. Customer care approach
- v. Increasing investment of Information Technology

The quality of information is related with achievement of goals in an organisation

Fig-3 Characteristics of Quality Information

CONCLUSIONS

There are many methods and way to analyzing an organisation. An organisation is a complex structure of formal and informal segments for smooth functioning of an organisation it is important to access difference between desired and achieved goal. Organisational effectiveness, depends on clarity of goals and responsibilities. So, organisational diagnosis is a method to check appropriateness of system subsystems and procedures. It plays a vital role to identify weakness and strength of the organisation. As we have discussed that in organisational diagnosis use different perspectives like sociological, functional technical etc. are being used. The role of management information System (MIS) facilitates communication channels for collaborative management and effective administration. MIS helps organisations to remain competitive and energetic to achieve goals. As we know information is the blood of organisation and management information system is the heart. Informed management becomes more effective and goal oriented. Management information system is a computer based system that imparts informative to manage operational goals basically providing descriptive, diagnostic, predictive and prescriptive informations. In this way, we can say management information system is the gist of organisational diagnostic procedure. This system fulfills information needs at all levels of organisation and helps making better and scientific decisions. Total Quality Management (TQM) could be achieved through management information system (MIS) because it creates a vivid and energetic work culture providing accurate data and informations.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Organisational Diagnosis and Assessment Bridging Theory and Practise- Michael Harrison Aric, Shirom 1998, Sage Publication New Delhi.
- [2]. Strategic Organisational Diagnosis and Design Developing Theory- Richard M Burton, Borge, Obel, 2012 KLUWER ACADEMIC Publication Boston Dordrecht/London
- [3]. Organisational Diagnosis- A Work book of Theory and Practice M.R. Weisbord, 1978, Basic Book Publisher.
- [4]. Leading Organisational Development and Change- Principles and Contextual Perspective – Rianu Singh, Shalini Ramdeo Springer Publication 2020.
- [5]. Organisational Development and Change Thomas- G. CCumming, Chirstopher. G Worely, 2001, South Western College Publication, Cornell Univ.
- [6]. Organisational Diagnosis- Harry Lerison Janice etc. 1972, Harverd Univ. Press.
- [7]. Organisational Diagnosis and Organisation Development Modal : Horizon Research Publication.
- [8]. नई संगठनात्मक संस्कृति ईज्ञानकोष
- [9]. संगठनात्मक व्यवहार (पुस्तक) – साहित्य भवन प्रकाशन
- [10]. NCERT Books
- [11]. IGNOU, MGSE unit III to VII
- [12]. India Today
- [13]. Jansatta